

Fighting the COVID-19 pandemic is a good rehearsal for tackling the global challenges the world will have to face in the 21st century. If we are smart, we can learn a lot from it.

COVID-19 is more than a pandemic

By KOEN DE BOSSCHERE

Small crises lead to small changes; large crises lead to large changes. COVID-19 is a large crisis but, at this moment in time, it is hard to tell what its long-term impact on society and the economy will be. One thing is sure: we will all make a distinction between the time before the coronavirus and the time after the coronavirus, and the new normal is very likely to be different from the old normal, no matter how hard people try to go back to the latter. Historically, it might become as impactful as the fall of the Berlin Wall, or 9/11.

Although it is still premature to talk about the new normal, it is good to start thinking about it by analysing how society is dealing with COVID-19 at the moment, and by looking at the trends and trying to imagine how they will evolve in the near future.

Key insights

- Thanks to all the previous efforts to digitize society and the economy, Western countries were ready to go online quickly and without major disruption to essential services. A stable broadband internet connection at home has proven to be as essential as water and electricity.
- Adapting to COVID-19 has caused innovation and digitization to speed up, which will create huge opportunities for the computing industry in the coming years: more online services and automation in all economic sectors, more remote working, more e-commerce, for example.
- Technology formed a major part of the COVID-19 response; for example, test and trace, or the shift to online learning. However, campaigners and educators have raised the alarm over privacy concerns, or technology being used as a substitute for in-person education, for example.
- The post-COVID world will be different from the pre-COVID world: politically, economically, and societally. COVID-19 is a once-in-a-lifetime opportunity to redesign the world we live in.

Key recommendations

- Europe should use the momentum generated by the COVID-19 pandemic to speed up digitalization of Europe by investing in broadband access for all, 5G, e-commerce, smart transportation, smart cities, ... while at the same time working on the European Green Deal.
- Investment in made-in-Europe technologies such as semiconductors could lead to greater resilience in the face of major supply-chain disruptions in the future.
- The use of technology to help manage a major event like a pandemic should always be accompanied by the appropriate safeguards and human resources to avoid issues with trust.
- Digital technologies to help manage supply chains, such as next-generation tracking technologies for the internet of things (IoT), should be a priority for funding. The roll-out of 5G will be instrumental in this sense.

Introduction

When COVID-19 emerged in late 2019, most people could not imagine the impact it was going to have on the world. In the space of just three months, it spread to every continent, initially leading to the isolation of individuals, followed by a lockdown of cities and eventually a lockdown of whole countries in spring and autumn 2020. Only essential workers were allowed to go to work. All non-essential businesses had to close and large gatherings, including activities in schools and higher education institutions, were forbidden for months. Private mobility was severely restricted. Cities and countries came to a standstill.

Most European countries succeeded in reducing case numbers enough to allow them to cautiously reopen the economy by June, in time for the summer holiday season. However, only weeks after the start of the holiday season, the number of cases started rising again, eventually leading to a resurgence (the “second wave”) in autumn. It then became clear that without the vaccination of the global population, the virus would continue to spread, leading to massive economic and human losses.

Massive vaccination in many countries took place in the first semester of 2021. Some countries were able to convince 90% of the adult population to get vaccinated, while there was much more hesitance and in some cases even resistance in other countries. Governments created COVID passes for people who were either fully vaccinated, had recovered from COVID-19, or had been recently tested to control access to public events and some businesses. One of the objectives was to convince more people to get vaccinated. Some governments and organizations even mandated vaccination among particular groups (healthcare, education and transportation workers or older citizens, for example).

In autumn 2021 came the big disappointment when it became clear that being vaccinated was not enough to stop the virus, and most countries once again had to impose restrictions while at the same time protecting the population with a booster shot. With the arrival of the Omicron vari-

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ant, the number of cases reached unprecedented levels. It has become clear that the coronavirus is not going to disappear in the coming year(s), that new variants will pop up, that the pharmaceutical industry will have to keep searching for better solutions to contain the virus, and that governments will have to closely monitor the situation.

The virus impacts the economy and the society in a variety of ways. In the early days, we had to stop its spreading because the healthcare system did not have enough personal protective equipment (PPE) for healthcare workers, and there were not enough ventilators to help the patients that needed them. When that problem was solved, we had to stop the spreading of the virus in order not to overwhelm the healthcare system. Non-urgent surgical procedures had to be postponed because there were not enough hospital beds left for non-COVID care, and some people died because they could not get the medical care they needed.

In autumn 2021, thanks to the vaccination programme, fewer infected people ended up in hospital beds, but the large number of cases had another side effect. Many people got infected at work, in school or at home, and had to quarantine. In the public sector, some schools had to close because too many teachers were in quarantine, public transportation had to reduce its service because too many drivers had to isolate at home, and hospitals did not have enough health professionals to serve all the hospital beds. As a result, the healthcare

system was once more stressed to its limits. In the private sector, pubs, bars, restaurants, theatres and nightclubs were open in many countries, but many people didn't feel comfortable visiting them, and some businesses incurred major losses. Therefore, even without lockdown, there is an economic and societal cost.

For most people, more than anything else, the virus has impacted their lifestyle: less social interaction, less travel, fewer events, less personal freedom. Many people have struggled to believe that this is happening to them in the 21st century, and still hope that it is just an ordinary nightmare. Unfortunately, it is a reality, and it is both sobering and humbling.

COVID-19 is without any doubt the biggest economic and social experiment of the early 21st century. Such an experiment creates unprecedented learning opportunities: what went well, what went wrong, who was forgotten, how to motivate people to follow the rules or to get vaccinated, what is the role of science in dealing with a global crisis, and how can we take advantage of this situation to do better in the future?

The situation is often compared with the so-called ‘Spanish flu’ of 1918-1919, which infected about 500 million people, killing 50 million. It is also compared with the Black Death of 1347-1351, which led to an estimated death toll of 75-200 million people. Both pandemics led not only to a lot of human suffering but also to profound and lasting societal and economic change.

The Black Death dramatically improved the standard of living of the masses (due to a shortage in the labour force, they could negotiate better conditions), and it eventually marked the end of feudalism in Europe and the onset of the early Renaissance. The Spanish flu in time led to public health-care systems and socialized medicine and healthcare [1, 2].

COVID-19 so far has infected more than 600 million people, and killed more than 6.5 million. The lower death toll is a result of a better medical system, but it is still huge, even in advanced industrial economies: more than 350 million cases with more than 2.3 million deaths. What lasting societal and economic changes will follow from this pandemic?

The impact of COVID-19 on society

Crises always put stress on systems, and when a system is stressed, its strengths and weaknesses are exposed. Many Asian countries did remarkably well in controlling the virus by acting immediately on every outbreak. Many countries in Africa also did better than expected given the relatively low vaccination rates on the continent. The resilience they need to survive in a normal situation might have helped them deal with the COVID-19 virus and its effects. Some wealthy countries struggled much more with the virus. Democratic governments tend to need more time to make decisions. They were hesitant to take drastic measures to stop the virus in the hope of protecting their (large) economies as much as possible. Unfortunately, viruses spread exponentially, and slow decision making helps the virus to spread, leading to additional economic and human devastation.

One notable case is the United States, where the 2020 presidential election campaign coincided with and became, in a sense, part of the pandemic. Policy was determined not only by public health considerations but also by electoral considerations, and by the choice between *people first* and *economy first*. Wearing a face mask eventually became a political statement rather than an effective public health measure. The same happened with vaccines. Social media and fake news subsequently

Figure 1: COVID-19 will not be the last global crisis (Source: <https://mackaycartoons.net>)

deepened the polarization, and expanded it into adjacent areas: vaccination in general, the credibility of scientists, the use of the COVID pass, etc.

In Europe, over 30 sovereign countries had to fight the pandemic in their own territory, with their own resources. The public healthcare systems of most European countries did not collapse and were able to give care to the patients who needed it (but still with a high death toll). One COVID-19 patient on a ventilator for one month takes the same intensive care resources as ten patients with open heart surgery. The consequence was that regular health care had to be postponed, leading to long waiting times for surgery between the COVID-waves.

For the first wave, one could argue that the virus was new, and that we were not prepared, but that argument does not hold for the subsequent waves. They were accurately predicted by the scientists, and still they caught Europe and the US off guard while Asian countries were more effective in their response. This brings back reminiscences of the 2008 financial crisis that we could not prevent and did not manage very well. Both events are damaging for the reputation of the United States and Europe, especially in Asia and in the Pacific. One day, these countries might question the

pre-eminence of the United States and Europe in some areas and start wondering why, for example, the head of the World Bank is always an American and the IMF always European. Hence COVID-19 might eventually change the world order (a bit) [13].

The impact of COVID-19 on the economy

Many economists were hoping that, after a short pandemic, the economy would experience a quick V-shaped recovery. Governments have been keeping the economy going by financially supporting businesses and citizens during the lockdown. In 2021, many governments approved recovery plans to boost the economy through public spending. The American Recue plan by the US government is probably the best known. Europe created its Next Generation EU, a landmark instrument for recovering from the coronavirus pandemic. Both plans want to combine recovery with the acceleration of the green and digital transition.

Unfortunately, the early recovery was hampered by broken supply chains, and a lack of workers. Most notable were the shortage of digital components, which caused production problems in the manufacturing industry, especially in the car industry. Europe and the US want to avoid

such problems in the future by creating local production of chips, and many investments have already been announced. Hopefully this will not lead to overproduction in the coming years and lost investments.

The lack of workers has a different origin. Many workers active in sectors that were closed for a long time (such as hospitality and events) decided to search for a new job, often better paid, and with better working conditions. Some foreign workers returned to their home countries to join their families during the lockdown. They did not return to their old jobs. Some restaurants were forced to reduce their opening hours or adapt their menus simply because they could not find the staff they needed. In addition, the ageing of the population has continued and millions of people retired during the pandemic, while thousands of working adults died from COVID, or are still suffering from the consequences. Several sectors are facing severe difficulties finding qualified candidates for vacancies. The recovery plans will give an additional boost to the economy, which might further increase the war for talent.

Hence, the economic impact depends on the sector. The sectors that were severely hit (events, tourism, hospitality) might need a long time to fully recover, even after the end of COVID, and some might never recover because customers have discovered good alternatives like online meetings instead of meetings in airport hotels. These businesses will have to scale down, and some of them might even go out of business. According to the Federal Reserve Chairman Jerome Powell, the economy as we knew it might be over because the pandemic has accelerated the introduction of technology, e-commerce, telework and automation. It might take years to for the market to adjust [12].

A shrinking economy leads to shrinking tax revenue, and lower public spending (or increased debts). This is a double whammy: after all the extra expenses incurred to fight the virus, countries will need more money to support their economies and their social security systems (health care, unemployment benefits) at the very time that the income is decreasing. Together with the

rising costs associated with an ageing population and investments to fight climate change, this turns the aftermath of the pandemic into a perfect storm for years to come. In such a budget situation, countries might become more self-centric, focused on their own problems, and less willing to help each other, or refuse to contribute to international organizations. This is unfortunate because global challenges like COVID-19 or climate change can only be tackled by international collaboration. No country is able to solve these problems on its own.

The supply chain problems inevitably lead to higher costs, and the worker shortage leads to higher wages for hard-to-find profiles. This will increase inflation, and the cost of living in general, potentially leading to more poverty and inequality in the western countries.

At the same time, this situation is also a once in a lifetime opportunity to introduce change. Mass tourism had become a burden in many places (Venice is planning to put restrictions on the number of daily visitors after Venetians discovered how much nicer the city was in the summers of 2020 and 2021), and air travel is one of the causes of climate change. Ecologists have long been advocating short food supply chains. Some countries have been trying to bring back manufacturing from lower-wage countries.

Some economists are advocating new economic models like the ‘doughnut economy’, which tries to achieve a balance between the social foundation (decent living for 10 billion people), and the ecological ceiling (the biocapacity of Planet Earth) [4], or other economic models that look not only at growth but also at other metrics to assess progress. All these models encourage governments to no longer invest in old industries with a large carbon footprint, but instead to invest in a green recovery [3] by supporting companies that work on sustainable solutions. Europe seems eager to take that path [11].

If we act smartly, the COVID-19 recession offers a unique opportunity to replace lost jobs with more sustainable jobs that compensate for the losses. Unfortunately, this will take some time.

Sovereignty

COVID-19 has exposed a weakness in the global market. The international supply chains on which many countries rely for essential goods are not guaranteed to work well in the case of a major international crisis. In normal circumstances, if demand goes up, production is increased, and everything goes back to normal. This works well in the absence of natural disasters, export restrictions, war, etc.

The COVID-19 crisis has shown how dependent all countries are on the rest of

Figure 2: Evolution of the shares of big tech companies since the lockdown in mid-March.

SOCIETAL DIMENSION

the world. Most countries were not able to quickly produce the personal protective equipment (PPE) and the testing equipment they needed. Over the course of recent decades, many countries gave up manufacturing low-cost commodity products, because they could be bought at a cheaper price in low-wage countries. At the same time, stockpiles were reduced because money could be saved by ordering as and when required. This works fine in a normal situation, but not in a global pandemic where a large part of the planet is in lockdown, and where the whole world is simultaneously and frantically trying to buy the same products (ranging from facemasks to ventilators to toilet paper). Setting up large-scale local manufacturing in a crisis situation is not simple and takes time. Even after six months, some countries were still struggling to get enough PPE for hospitals and nursing homes. This lack of PPE has led directly to the loss of thousands of healthcare workers across the world.

There is a lesson to be learned from this experience. Optimizing supply chains by buying from the cheapest supplier, and eliminating all buffers to save money, kills resilience. Even without man-made export restrictions, there can be situations in which supply chains are broken by external causes (natural disasters, war, global hoarding/stockpiling). For essential goods and raw materials, it is wise to always have at least one local source. It is worrisome that, today, some essential life-saving drugs are produced in a very small number of countries (90% of all penicillin is produced in

China; Europe no longer produces paracetamol [7]). Europe could consider making a requirement that essential goods like commodity medical equipment and life-saving drugs that are admitted to the European market are also (partially) produced in Europe.

Broken supply chains eventually get restored, and all the stakeholders involved work together to restore them as soon as possible. Export and import restrictions are totally different. They are political (e.g. to protect a country's own industry, or as a retaliation measure), which means that the industrial stakeholders involved can do little to lift the restrictions (especially if they were imposed by a different country). Only politicians can do this, and the interests of a handful of companies might not weigh enough to change relations between countries.

The growing interest in sovereignty will unavoidably lead to further deglobalization, which has been an ongoing process over the last decade [7].

COVID-19 accelerates digital transformation

The sudden lockdowns in many countries forced companies and organizations to figure out how they could continue their operations under the restrictions and stay-at-home orders. Projects that would normally take months or years to implement were implemented in days, weeks or

Who led the digital transformation of your company?

- A) CEO
- B) CTO
- C) COVID-19

Figure 3: COVID-19 was in 2020 a main driver for digital transformation (Source: <https://journal.laurea.fi/welcome-our-new-digital-transformation-officer-COVID-19/>)

months. Examples of transformations that happened almost overnight are:

- Cashless payments. Today an increasing number of businesses simply refuse to accept cash. In some countries, shops are now obliged to accept card payments. Such a transition would normally take years to complete in a cash-based economy, and require extra legislation. It is not likely that cash will make a massive comeback after COVID-19.
- Online teaching and testing. This was completely uncharted territory for most primary and secondary schools, but it has now become common in many places. For higher education, online teaching was not new, but the speed at which it was scaled up is unseen. Thanks to COVID-19, online teaching has found a permanent place in education.
- Digital signing. Wet signatures on paper are impractical under stringent stay-at-home orders. It did not take long for digital signatures to be widely accepted for most documents that need to be signed. It is unlikely that wet signatures will come back. Governments should instead work on the infrastructure to support digital signatures.
- E-commerce. Companies that had invested in creating an online business before COVID-19 did not have to completely close their business during the lockdown and could continue to serve their customers. Major online shops experienced a large increase in trading, as did the shipping and courier companies. The fact that Amazon became one of the most valuable companies on the planet is no surprise (Figure 2).

Figure 4: Levels are historically high.

- Remote working. Stay-at-home orders led to unemployment for people working in non-essential jobs that could not be done remotely and to working from home for the rest. Whereas office work used to be the norm, and remote working the exception (often granted to the employee as a favour), telework has now become very common in many companies. Employers' attitudes towards home working have changed, and many employees have discovered its advantages (no time lost to commuting, more flexibility). Office work is returning, but it will not replace all telework. This evolution will also impact the real estate market. Many people are looking for an apartment or a house with an extra room for a home office. Companies are looking for smaller offices, and instead offer financial incentives to employees to work from home.
- Online meetings. Many people have discovered online video meetings during the lockdown period and have learned that they are quite convenient for certain types of meetings. After COVID-19, online meetings will stay with us. Even medical doctors discovered that they could diagnose some of their patients remotely via a video chat – completely eliminating the risk of infection.

It is almost a miracle that this transition was able to happen so fast with the lock-

down and stay-at-home-orders in place. This was only possible thanks to the fact that all the underlying technologies and infrastructure were already in place, and were ready to be scaled up via huge global data centres. Industry was ready for it; it only had to push the button.

Lockdown and social distancing also created opportunities for innovative digital startups, which saw a surge in the adoption of their solutions, like companies producing rapid tests, vaccines, CO2 meters, protective solutions, It is fair to say that COVID-19 has spurred innovation, and that it is an accelerator for the adoption of digital technologies. Several of the solutions will become permanent and there is a huge opportunity for the computing industry to launch new solutions.

COVID-19 increases inequality

COVID-19 has impacted the less educated more than it has the well-educated and has affected women more than men. The reason is clear: those with lower levels of education more often carry out jobs that were affected by the lockdown (retail, hospitality) or carry out essential jobs (food preparation, cleaning, nursing, transport), which exposed them more to the virus (and to the costs of a treatment in the event of infection). Those with higher

levels of education are more likely to have office jobs that can be done from home (teachers, managers, accountants), and they live in better homes, making it easier for them to stay at home and avoid infection. A stay-at-home order is simpler in a suburban house with a garden, a pool and a broadband internet connection than in a one-bedroom apartment in a city.

But there is more. The impact of COVID-19 also has a varying impact on the different generations.

- Children will forever remember the year that they did not have to go to school. Children from underprivileged families were severely hit (for example, there may have been no computer at home for online lessons, no daily hot meal at school, overcrowded homes). This might have a lasting impact on their further development. Children from middle-class families might experience a far less negative impact from COVID-19.
- University students (generation Z or “zoomers”) were suddenly studying at an online university, and many decided to move back to their parents' home after having lived away for a couple of years. This has social implications for both the students and their parents. Students found it more difficult to find student jobs (which had previously often been in bars and restaurants) to help pay for their studies.
- Working parents with young children (the millennials) had a hard time too. They had to find a solution for their children who could not attend school, and were expected to help them with their schoolwork. At the same time, they also had to work full time, either at the workplace or at home.
- Working or recently retired people in the 50-70 age group (baby-boomers) were probably hit the least. They are unlikely to have to combine caring for young children with a job, and their age group was less vulnerable than the over-70s.

Depending on how long it takes to overcome COVID-19, the intergenerational solidarity between the boomers and the zoomers might be severely tested. The baby boom generation is now 55+, has built up

some wealth and has recently retired or is looking forward to retirement. Many of them were not hit hard by COVID-19 or the recession. The zoomers, however, are now entering higher education. They will have to pay taxes to pay back the public debt incurred during the pandemic, for climate action and to support the ageing population (boomers and older). Debt levels have now surpassed the global debt level seen at the end of the Second World War (expressed at % of GDP, see Figure 4) [10].

When the boomers pass away, their wealth will be transferred to the zoomers' parents (millennials), not to the zoomers. Hence COVID-19 might lead to serious discussions about new forms of intergenerational solidarity [5, 6].

Conclusion

COVID-19 is more than a pandemic; it has the potential to change the world as we know it. We will have to make the right decisions and change the world for the better: more sustainable, more equal, more diverse.

COVID-19 is also a good rehearsal for climate action [8]. For several years, we have known what the problem is, and what needs to be done to solve it. It will require international collaboration, new technologies, and a lifestyle change, but at a much larger scale. Let's use the lessons learned from COVID-19 to tackle that challenge [9].

It is important to imagine the world you want in 2040, and then to work towards it, one step at a time. The world needs visionaries to show the rest of the world the possibilities.

References

- [1] Kate Whiting, "A science journalist explains how the Spanish flu changed the world", <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/04/COVID-19-how-spanish-flu-changed-world/>.
- [2] Lawrence Wright, "How Pandemics Wreak Havoc – and open minds", <https://www.newyorker.com/magazine/2020/07/20/how-pandemics-wreak-havoc-and-open-minds>
- [3] David Watts, "Global sustainable development in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic", <https://ieep.eu/news/global-sustainable-development-in-the-aftermath-of-the-COVID-19-pandemic>
- [4] Kate Raworth, "Meet the doughnut: the new economic model that could help end inequality", <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2017/04/the-new-economic-model-that-could-end-inequality-doughnut/>
- [5] Dave Lee, "The Recessionals: Why COVID-19 is another cruel setback for millennials", <https://www.straitstimes.com/opinion/the-recessionals-why-COVID-19-is-another-cruel-setback-for-millennials>
- [6] Kendra Cherry, "How Different Generations Are Responding to COVID-19", <https://www.verywellmind.com/how-different-generations-are-responding-to-COVID-19-4802517>
- [7] Josep Borrell, "The post-coronavirus world is already here", https://www.ecfr.eu/publications/summary/the_post_coronavirus_world_is_already_here
- [8] Dania Eel Akkawi, "Climate Change and COVID-19: There Is More Than One Curve to Flatten", <https://www.thecairoreview.com/midan/climate-change-and-COVID-19-there-is-more-than-one-curve-to-flatten>
- [9] Bill Gates, "COVID-19 is awful. Climate change could be worse", <https://www.gatesnotes.com/Energy/Climate-and-COVID-19>
- [10] Martin Wolf, "The threat of long economic Covid looms", <https://www.ft.com/content/f9a0c784-712e-4bf9-b994-55f8d63316d9>
- [11] "A European Green Deal", https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en
- [12] "The economy as we knew it might be over, Fed Chairman says", <https://edition.cnn.com/2020/11/12/economy/economy-after-covid-powell/index.html>
- [13] Sven Biscop, "Can corona cure our superiority complex?", <https://www.egmontinstitute.be/can-corona-cure-our-superiority-complex/>

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